

Integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HRM in countering threats of technology leakage, insider threats and cyber-attacks in industrial environment

*A Project Report submitted in part fulfillment of the requirements
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by

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Declaration

I, *Ruhul Amin Khan*, hereby declare that the project report titled “*Integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HRM in countering threats of technology leakage, insider threats and cyber-attacks in industrial environment*” is a bonafide work carried out by me under the guidance of *Prof. (Dr.) Subhrangshu Sekhar Sarkar*. I also declare that neither this work as a whole nor a part of it has been submitted to any other University or Institute for any other degree, diploma or award. I further declare that this written submission represents my ideas in my own words and where other’s ideas or words have been included, I have adequately cited and referenced the original sources. I affirm that I have adhered to all principles of academic honesty and integrity and have not misrepresented or falsified any idea/data/fact/source to the best of my knowledge. I understand that any violation of the above will cause for disciplinary action by the Institute and can also evoke penal action from the sources which have not been cited properly.

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Abstract

Globally, the industrial environment has been continuously evolving with technological advancements and innovation. Similarly, the nature of threats to the industrial landscape going beyond physical breaches such as in the form of insider threats, trade secret leakage and cyberattacks. This study is an endeavour to come up with an integrated security model which will bring together three verticals such as Physical Security, Cybersecurity and Human Resource Management (HRM) under one umbrella and check the efficiency of the integrated security model in countering security threats.

This study considered all the individual working in the Public Sector, Private Sector and Public Sector Undertakings with designations or roles such as Security Officer, HR Manager, IT/Cybersecurity Specialist, Operations Manager and General Administration etc. as the target population. The said target population has been further stratified into industry types viz. Manufacturing, IT & Technology, Energy & Utilities; Governance, Policy Making and Public Service; Healthcare; Defense / Law Enforcement etc. As the target population is relatively small, the survey's sample size was 54 respondents. The questionnaire designed considering the objectives of the study and variables. Microsoft Excel and online statistical tools have been used for hypothesis testing. This study considered number of independent variables while checking with the efficiency of the integrated security model. Based on findings, this study concludes with few recommendations with the headings as risk mitigation strategies, role of HR and supply chain security etc.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

“All warfare is based on deception - Sun Tzu”

Security is the perception of safety and the measures we adopt from time to time to secure the bodies and property of ourselves and others. Due to rapidly changing trends, the adoption of established practices cannot be claimed as 100% foolproof. Security, as a concept, often refers to the physical aspect. In current times, the term "security" has a varied connotation, primarily encompassing the implicit logical aspect, such as economic moats and protecting trade secrets. For instance, the Nuclear Program of Iran was physically secured by security personnel, but it was disrupted by a malicious program called Stuxnet. Key personnel responsible for the project's success were secretly killed, where adversaries intruded as suppliers, provided faulty hardware and compromised software. The key personnel of an organization are sometimes lured to join its competitors with the intention of exploiting competitive advantages, consequently putting pressure on the role of HR. Therefore, the scope of Industrial Security cannot be confined solely to one vertical i.e. Physical Security which is focused on protection of tangible assets such as man, materials and machines; it must encompass the logical aspects of security. This study is an endeavour to integrate security verticals which are currently in silos with elements viz. information security, periodic security audits, procurement policy, protection of supply chain and checklists for HR etc.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

A glance through the existing literature reveals that the industrial environments often encountered with the evolving threats such as technology leakage, insider threats and cyberattacks emphasizing the need for a robust security framework integrating the physical security, cybersecurity and Human Resource Management (HRM) under one umbrella. Importantly, the literature scattered across cyberspace putting all together paves the way for understanding these verticals individually, developing a connection between each vertical.

2.2 Key terms:

2.2.1 Technology leakage and Insider threat

Yu and Chang (2020) in their meta-analysis, highlighted the concern for increased technology leakage in South Korea stressing the need for protecting business activities and loss prevention. In the event of technology leakage, insiders who possess the right to access the systems tend to divulge technology rather than outsiders. Further, categorized the modus operandi of such crimes in terms of the amount of technology used while committing the crime of technology leakage such as low-tech, high-tech and no-tech. One ex-employee using USB drive to extract valuable customer information and sell it to a competitor can be considered as low-tech modus operandi. Consequently, another employee well acquainted with the vulnerabilities to the system, facilitating access to others to exploit the system may be categorized under high-tech modus operandi.

Coping up with the threat of trade secret / technology leakage, companies which strive to develop competitive advantage, makes it harder for competitors to hijack their market share. Companies with wide economic moat seems having robust competitive advantages for protecting its market share. Contrarily, companies having less competitive advantage where new entrants can easily replicate the ideas are more vulnerable to competition.

Notably, trade secrets like any other Intellectual Property are not registered. As of doing this study, there is no specific legislation in the legal framework of India for protection of trade secrets. If such incident get reported, at best cases will be registered under the provisions of Information Technology Act, Copyright Act with latest amendments and general provisions of

Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita. Therefore, if such crime is committed there is less chance of conviction in the court of law.

This highlights the need for a specific legislation for protection of trade secrets in India.

2.2.2 Supply chains and digital assets

Bar-Zohar and Mishal in their book Mossad discussed how Stuxnet, the malicious program took control of “*Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA)*” system causing damage to Iran’s nuclear program. It indicates the vulnerability of an organization’s supply chain against the threats of malicious software or faulty hardware from suppliers. Further, it puts a question mark on the existing procurement process and the security of supply chain.

2.2.3 Security of Key Personnel / Person in high authority in Business and Critical Projects

The five scientists associated with the Iran’s nuclear program were killed allegedly by foreign elements between the year 2010 to 2020. Every organization’s core business in generally lies in the hands of few key personnel and their sudden absence in the event of death, resignation or hired by competitor can cause significant damage to the business.

“Sun Tzu: The control of the large force is the same principle as the control of a few men: it is merely a question of diving up their members.”

2.2.4 In the Context of Assam - Talukdar & Kalita (Book: ULFA)

The North-Eastern part of India, especially the state of Assam witnessed a prolonged period of insurgency in the region since 1979. During insurgency key personnel of vital industrial installations and business houses were the common target for exploitation and ransom demand. Primarily, the Oil India Installations in the Upper Assam part confronted massive amount of insurgency. In the 21st June 1988, Senior Public Relation Official of Oil India Ltd, Duliajan was shot dead. Two day after, on 23rd June Chief Personal Officer of Hindustan Fertilizer Corporation, Namrup was gunned down. On 6th July ULFA took the responsibility of such killing.

In the 20th January 1990, President of Guwahati Chambers of Commerce was shot dead by ULFA. On 9th April 1990, President of Assam Frontier Tea Estate was killed by ULFA. Consecutively, in the same year on 16th July, General Manager of Guwahati Oil Refinery

including his son and driver was abducted. On 23rd January 1991, Drilling Engineer of Oil India Ltd, Duliajan was killed.

In the 30th June 1991, when there was a power shift in the political setup of Assam, within 24 hours of oath-taking, 15 key personnel were abducted from various places, among them were Chief Geophysicist, Dy. General Manager, Executive Engineer and Assistant Engineer of Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. In the year 1997 during October, Intelligence Bureau revealed that ULFA exploiting senior officials of Tata Tea, finally with the intervention of Ratan Tata, the then Managing Director of Tata Sons with the help of the then Chief Minister of Assam, the contention came to an end.

2.3 Summary: Literature Review

The review of existing literature highlights the need for a comprehensive approach towards industrial security considering three verticals at once where physical security for the tangible assets comprising Man – Material - Machine, cybersecurity for digital assets and HRM for managing the workforce dealing with insider threats and technology leakage etc by developing SOPs, standards, checklists and policies.

Nityanandam in "Standards for Physical Security Management in Industry" focused on developing standards and protocols in maintaining security in an industrial environment. In his work, explaining the concepts of access control, perimeter security, intrusion detection and surveillance systems, advocated for significant investment on technology and setting up of security department separated from HR. Further, his work acknowledged that physical security in silos is insufficient countering insider threats and cyberattacks, which can be construed as implicitly in favour of integration of verticals working in silos.

Chapter 3: Research Gap, Objectives, Scope and Limitations

3.1 Research Gap:

By and large existing literature discusses individual security domains in silos, while few studies stress on developing a holistic model for a comprehensive security in an industrial environment. However, empirical studies as to how integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HR all together can enhance industrial security are yet to be explored. Further, it raises another question, whether such integration model can be feasible across various industry types such as manufacturing, IT & Technology, Energy & Utilities and Defense etc.

3.2 Research Question:

The research gap lands with the question-

“How the integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HRM will enhance industrial security addressing the evolving threats of technology leakage, insider threats and cyber-attacks in industrial environments?”

3.3 Objectives:

Broadly the study will focus on the following:

- i. Whether a security plan that integrates Physical, Cybersecurity and Human Resource Management under one umbrella can enhance efficiency.
- ii. How the growing threat of industrial technology leakage, insider threats and cyberattacks in industrial environments are affecting businesses.
- iii. Whether a layered security approach such as Perimeter Intrusion Detection Systems, Identity & Access Management and a secure communication channel are all together effective in mitigate cyberattacks.
- iv. What will be role of HR in the context of security and preparing the workforce during security crises.
- v. Evaluation of other areas for enhancement of security such as awareness programs, supply chain security and existing legal framework in countering industrial technology leakage, insider threats and cyberattacks.

3.4 Scope & Limitations:

3.4.1 Scope:

This study is primarily about integration of components such as physical security, cybersecurity & HRM and checking the effectiveness of the integrated security model against threats such as Technology leakage, insider threats and cyberattacks. The study confined with these threats and for the purpose of the study, effectiveness of the integrated security model have been checked broadly by segregating the industries into public sector, private sector and PSUs. This study primarily considered industrial installations within the state of Assam, however, few respondents in public / private sector out of the spheres of Assam could be reached via email and instant messaging apps. Further, during the course of the study, other aspects associated with the core question viz. the role of HRM, procurement policy, security of supply chain, uses of cybersecurity tools, risk mitigation strategies and training modules etc. in various organizations have been revisited.

3.4.2 Limitations:

This study aimed at analysing the current security scenario in various industrial environments and it is a fact that every organization would be cautious and calculative in giving responses. However, in order to elicit unbiased responses utmost care have been maintained while designing and distributing the questionnaire that no information can be linked with specific organization and designations. Further, this study narrowed down the target population in various strata, as to why sample size stands at 54 (fifty-four) that may be relatively small.

Chapter 4:

Research Methodology

All the individuals working in the Public Sector, Private Sector and Public Sector Undertakings with designations or roles viz. Security Officer, HR Manager, IT/Cybersecurity Specialist, Operations Manager and General Administration are the target population. Further, the target population has been stratified into industry types such as Manufacturing, IT & Technology, Energy & Utilities; Governance, Policy Making and Public Service; Healthcare; Defense / Law Enforcement and Academia. The study used survey questionnaire designed in Google Forms and shared the questionnaire link via instant messaging app 'WhatsApp' for reaching distant respondents. The people working in the aforesaid designations and roles were considered respondents. The questionnaire did not ask for identifiable information such as names and specific designations with the intention of eliciting unbiased responses. Although, email had been captured for authenticity and limiting to one response per respondent. As the target population is relatively small, the survey's sample size was 54 respondents. Further, considering the research question respondents were randomly selected using stratified sampling technique. The questionnaire designed considering objectives of the study and variables. Quantitative data was collected from respondents eliciting ratings in a 5-point Likert scale mostly with closed questions such as How Effective, Satisfactory level, How Vulnerable, How Important etc. Single response out of many options through radio buttons and many responses out of many options through checkboxes selected by the respondents. Microsoft Excel, online statistical tool with the URL: <https://www.socscistatistics.com> and Google Form summary diagrams have been used for analysis.

Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Interpretation

5.1 Whether integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HRM can enhance industrial security

Primary question of this study was to see whether integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HRM can enhance industrial security.

Questionnaire addressed the following questions to the respondents in order to elicit the effectiveness of organizations' current layered security as dependent variable and integration of individual components such as Physical Security, Cybersecurity and HRM as independent variable.

Response summary for “Which of the following components are included in your organization’s existing security plan? (may select multiple)”

Fig.1

Response summary for “Effectiveness of your organizations’ current layered security in mitigating security threats”

Fig.2

Null Hypothesis

The mean effectiveness of organizations' current layered security with full integration is equal to the mean effectiveness of organizations' current layered security without integration.

$$H_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_0$$

Where,

μ_1 = Mean effectiveness of organizations with full integration (Physical Security + Cybersecurity + HRM)

μ_0 = Mean effectiveness of organizations without full integration (less than 3)

Alternative Hypothesis

The mean effectiveness of organizations' current layered security with full integration is not equal to the mean effectiveness of organizations' current layered security without integration.

$$H_1 : \mu_1 \neq \mu_0$$

Organizations with three components (Physical Security+ Cybersecurity+ HRM) are encoded as 1 for Yes and if less than three encoded as 0 for No.

Effectiveness rating of Respondent's Organization with full integration = (3, 5, 5, 3, 5, 4, 4, 5, 4, 1, 3, 4, 4, 4)

Effectiveness rating of Respondent's Organization without full integration = (3, 2, 3, 2, 3, 2, 2, 1, 2, 3, 3, 4, 3, 3, 3, 4, 2, 1, 3, 4, 5, 1, 2, 4, 1, 2, 2, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2, 3, 2, 3, 2, 2, 1)

MS Excel - Data Analysis

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances		
	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	3.857142857	2.55
Variance	1.208791209	0.920512821
Observations	14	40
Pooled Variance	0.992582418	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	52	
t Stat	4.225099089	
P(T<=t) one-tail	4.82648E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.674689154	
P(T<=t) two-tail	9.65296E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.006646805	

Table . 1

Online statistical tool (*socscistatistics*)

Sample: 1

$$N_1: 14$$

$$df_1 = N - 1 = 14 - 1 = 13$$

$$M_1: 3.86$$

$$SS_1: 15.71$$

$$s^2_1 = SS_1/(N - 1) = 15.71/(14-1) = 1.21$$

Sample: 2

$$N_2: 40$$

$$df_2 = N - 1 = 40 - 1 = 39$$

$$M_2: 2.55$$

$$SS_2: 35.9$$

$$s^2_2 = SS_2/(N - 1) = 35.9/(40-1) = 0.92$$

T-value Calculation

$$s^2_p = ((df_1/(df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_1) + ((df_2/(df_2 + df_2)) * s^2_2) = ((13/52) * 1.21) + ((39/52) * 0.92) = 0.99$$

$$s^2_{M1} = s^2_p/N_1 = 0.99/14 = 0.07$$

$$s^2_{M2} = s^2_p/N_2 = 0.99/40 = 0.02$$

$$t = (M_1 - M_2)/\sqrt{(s^2_{M1} + s^2_{M2})} = 1.31/\sqrt{0.1} = 4.23$$

The *t*-value is 4.2251. The *p*-value is .000097. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

In support of the alternate hypothesis, it is observed that the mean effectiveness of organizations' security with full integration $M_1: 3.86$ is much higher than without integration $M_2: 2.55$ which indicates more efficiency with full integration.

Type of Industry and Effectiveness Rating

Type of Industry	Which of the following components are included in your organization's existing security plan?	Rate the effectiveness of your organization's current layered security
IT & Technology	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	3
Governance, Policy Making and Public Service	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	5
IT & Technology	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	5
IT & Technology	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	3
IT & Technology	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	5
Energy & Utilities	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	4
Governance, Policy Making and Public Service	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	4
IT & Technology	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	5
Defense / Law Enforcement	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	4
Governance, Policy Making and Public Service	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	1
Governance, Policy Making and Public Service	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	3
Manufacturing	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	4
Energy & Utilities	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	4
Defense / Law Enforcement	Physical Security, Cybersecurity, HRM	4

Table. 2

Fig. 3

Organizations such as IT & Technology, Governance & Policy Making and Defense are more inclined towards integration with effectiveness rating between 4 to 5, while Healthcare and Academia shows less integration with low effectiveness rating.

24. How important is it to integrate physical security, cybersecurity and HRM into a single security plan to address industrial threats?
54 responses

Fig. 4

5.2 Whether Integration model is effective in countering industrial threats

The Hypothesis has been tested with another set of data points where 54 respondents rated the integration model in countering industrial threats as: (4, 3, 5, 3, 5, 5, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5, 3, 5, 3, 2, 1, 5, 4, 5, 5, 5, 5, 4, 4, 3, 5, 5, 1, 4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 1, 1, 1, 1, 5, 4, 5, 5, 4, 5, 5, 4, 5, 4, 5, 3, 3, 4, 5)

Null Hypothesis

The mean of rating for integrated model is equal to the mean of rating for non-integrated model.

$$H_0 : \mu \text{ integrated} - \mu \text{ non-integrated} = 0$$

Where,

$$\mu = 3 \text{ (Neutral as per Likert Scale)}$$

$$\mu \text{ integrated} = 4 \text{ to } 5$$

$$\mu \text{ non-integrated} = 1 \text{ to } 3$$

Alternative Hypothesis

The mean of rating for integrated model is greater than the mean of rating for non-integrated model.

$$H_1 : \mu \text{ integrated} - \mu \text{ non-integrated} > 0$$

Online statistical tool (*socscistatistics*)

$$\mu = 3 \text{ (Neutral)}$$

$$\text{Sample Mean } (\bar{x}) = 3.94$$

The t -value is 5.360722. The value of p is $< .00001$. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

This strongly rejects null hypothesis as p -value is very less.

5.3 Integration Model and Security Awareness

The hypothesis has been further tested with other independent variables such as whether organizations who conducts Security Awareness Program, do they give importance to the integration of components (physical security + cybersecurity + HRM).

14. Does your organization conduct Security Awareness Programs for employees?

54 responses

Fig. 5

Null Hypothesis

Security Awareness Program does not change importance to integration.

$$H_0 : \mu_{\text{Yes}} = \mu_{\text{No}}$$

Where,

μ_{Yes} = Mean of rating on the importance of Integration, when Security Awareness Program conducted

μ_{No} = Mean of rating on the importance of Integration, when Security Awareness Program not conducted

Alternative Hypothesis

Organizations who conduct Security Awareness Program they give more importance to integration.

$$H_1 : \mu_{\text{Yes}} > \mu_{\text{No}}$$

MS Excel - Data Analysis

t – Test : Two - Sample Assuming Equal Variance

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.24137931	3.6
Variance	0.97536946	2.333333333
Observations	29	25
Pooled Variance	1.60212202	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	52	
t Stat	1.85668947	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.03451214	
t Critical one-tail	1.67468915	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.06902427	
t Critical two-tail	2.00664681	

Table – 3

Online statistical tool (*socscistatistics*)

N_1 : 29

$$df_1 = N - 1 = 29 - 1 = 28$$

M_1 : 4.24

SS_1 : 27.31

$$s^2_1 = SS_1 / (N - 1) = 27.31 / (29 - 1) = 0.98$$

Sample 2

N_2 : 25

$$df_2 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$$

M_2 : 3.6

SS_2 : 56

$$s^2_2 = SS_2/(N - 1) = 56/(25-1) = 2.33$$

T-value Calculation

$$s^2_p = ((df_1/(df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_1) + ((df_2/(df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_2) = ((28/52) * 0.98) + ((24/52) * 2.33) = 1.6$$

$$s^2_{M1} = s^2_p/N_1 = 1.6/29 = 0.06$$

$$s^2_{M2} = s^2_p/N_2 = 1.6/25 = 0.06$$

$$t = (M_1 - M_2)/\sqrt{(s^2_{M1} + s^2_{M2})} = 0.64/\sqrt{0.12} = 1.86$$

The t-value is 1.85669. The p-value is .034512. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

In support of the Alternate Hypothesis it indicates that the organizations who conduct Security Awareness Program tend to give more importance to integrated security model.

Chapter 6: Findings and Recommendations

6.1 Findings

It is found that in organizations where layered security approach has been implemented such as Perimeter Intrusion Detection Systems (PIDS), Identity & Access Management (IAM), secure networks for OT (Operational Technology) and a secure communication channel they are more effective in mitigating security threats.

Organizations such as IT & Technology, Governance & Policy Making and Defense are found more inclined towards integrated security model with effectiveness rating between 4 to 5, while Healthcare and Academia shows less integration with low effectiveness rating.

It is found that organizations who conduct Security Awareness Program tend to give more importance to the integrated security model.

6.2 Recommendations

6.2.1 Risk mitigation Strategies

In the context of physical security, it is found that respondents prioritized Access Control mechanisms (biometric, entry pass etc), CCTV Surveillance and thirdly to the Secure Facility Design over the protection of physical property manned by security personnel. This is true in practical scenario, weak Facility Design requires more vigilance and increases overhead in terms of hiring more security personnel, procurement of security gadgets etc. In this regard, critical industrial installations can counter the threat of trespass through Perimeter Intrusion Detection Systems (PIDS).

26. Which physical security measures should be prioritized in an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 6

As per responses, it is observed that organizations opt for Multi – Factor Authentication and End-to-end encryption being the cost effective option that comes as default with many of the reputed software applications. However, organizations must limit access to key business areas. Further, damage to the systems scattered across various departments can be mitigated through Network Segmentation in the event of Ransomware or any other attack.

Further, respondents in the open-ended section of the questionnaire raised concern over the convergence of networks for Information Technology (IT) along with Operational Technology (OT) which tend to raise the cause of cyberattacks resulting in operational downtime and financial losses. Since convergence is the compulsion for business continuity, organizations must adhere to the standards with reference to the following responses for protecting their assets.

7. What security controls does your organization implement for Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) network protection? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 7

10. What cybersecurity tools and protocols are employed in your organization? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 8

27. Which cybersecurity measures should be prioritized in an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 9

25. Which of the following benefits do you expect from an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 10

6.2.2 Role of HR

As per responses, it is observed that organizations are mostly concerned with Insider Threats from the current employees, puts pressure on the HR in conducting Security Awareness programs, background checks of employees, periodic security audit and monitoring of insider threats through policy making.

2. Have you or your organization experienced any security threats related to: (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig - 11

3. What do you consider the primary source of insider threats in your organization? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig- 12

5. How frequently does your organization conduct security audits or risk assessments?

54 responses

Fig- 13

4. What are the most common causes of security breaches in your industry / organization? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig- 14

Fig- 15

13. What HR policies are in practice in your organization to mitigate insider threats? (may select multiple)
54 responses

Fig - 16

The National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB) through latest publication by February 2024 reported cybercrime of 50,035 in 2020 to 52,974 in 2021 (5.9%) which further increased to 65,893 in 2022 with a significant hike of 24.4% from 2021.

The focus of this study is to check for the efficiency of integrated security model in countering technology leakage, insider threats and cyber-attacks in industrial environments. Notably, as of doing this study, there is no specific legislation in the legal framework of India for protection of trade secrets. Therefore, if such crime is committed there is less chance of conviction in the court of law.

The data collected in this study shows that very few Security Awareness Programs include Cyber Law, Modus Operandi of Cybercriminals and procedure on Identifying, data collection, analysis and reporting of crimes. The HR while designing the training module may consider the following in the syllabus.

15. Which of the following topics are covered in HR led security training programs? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 17

16. How important is it for HR to collaborate with physical security and cybersecurity teams to address workforce related risks during a crisis?

54 responses

Fig. 18

6.2.3 Supply chain security

This is evident from the existing literature that intruders use to exploit the loopholes in the supply chain to disrupt the continuity of business. The data collected for this study shows that very few are concerned with the verification of malicious software or faulty hardware. It strongly suggests for revisiting the procurement policy, especially for the critical infrastructure and critical industrial installations before commissioning of new hardware or technological upgrades.

18. Which of the following measures are currently in practice to secure your supply chain? (may select multiple)

54 responses

Fig. 19

19. How vulnerable do you consider your organization's supply chain to threats like malicious software or faulty hardware from suppliers?

54 responses

Fig. 20

20. Rate the effectiveness of your organization's current procurement and supply chain security

54 responses

Fig. 21

6.2.4 Security of key personnel

Study of the existing literature shows that not only at the high level of strategic relation between Nations where scientists associated with the nuclear program of Iran were assassinated, at regional level in the North-Easter part of India, the common target were the key personnel associated with the vital industrial installations, mostly gunned down or kidnapped for ransom. Therefore, the Physical Security as a vertical while protecting tangible assets, it must consider the security of key personnel for smooth continuity of business.

21. Does your organization have specific security measures to identify and protect key personnel involved in critical projects or business operations?

54 responses

Fig. 22

22. Rate the effectiveness of your organization's current measures in protecting key personnel from threats such as assault, kidnapping and exploitation etc. (Optional)

53 responses

Fig. 23

Chapter 7: Conclusion and Scope of Future Work

It is observed from the findings that organizations where integration model has been implemented they are more effective in mitigating security threats. Notably, it is found that IT & Technology, Governance & Policy Making and Defense are more inclined towards integrated security model while Healthcare and Academia shows less integration with low effectiveness rating. It indicates a correlation between organization type and the degree of threats specific to the organizations in adoption of security model while countering threats. In this regard, future studies may be carried out specific to one industry for more accurate insights. As the industrial environment is dynamic and there may a significant shift in the threat trend, future studies can be carried out to check with other independent variables and efficiency of the integration model.

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Annexures

Questionnaire:

Survey on Industrial Security

"Integration of physical security, cybersecurity and HRM in countering threats of technology leakage, insider threats and cyber-attacks in industrial environment"

Since this form does not require names and specific designation, your responses will remain anonymous. It is strongly believed that with unbiased responses, real insights can be drawn to better address the evolving threats such as technology / trade secret leakage, insider threats and cyber- attacks.

*** Indicates required question**

Email *

Respondent Information

Designation/Role: *

- Security Officer HR Manager/Personnel IT/Cybersecurity Specialist
 Operations Manager General Administration Academia
 Other

Organization Type: *

- Public Sector Private Sector PSU (Public Sector Undertaking)

Type of Industry/Organization: *

- Manufacturing IT & Technology Energy & Utilities Governance, Policy Making and Public Service Healthcare Defense / Law Enforcement Academia

Years of Experience: *

- 0-5 years 6-10 years 11-15 years 16+ years

Part 1: Industrial / Organisational Technology / Trade Secret Leakage, Insider Threats & Intellectual Property Theft

1. How concerned are you about industrial technology/ Trade Secret leakage, insider threat and intellectual property theft in your organization? *Mark only one oval.*

- Not Concerned Slightly Concerned Moderately Concerned Highly Concerned Extremely Concerned

2. Have you or your organization experienced any security threats related to: (may select multiple)

- Technology leakage Insider threats (e.g. employees misusing their privilege of access)
 Cyberattacks Data breaches/Intellectual Property theft No such incidents

3. What do you consider the primary source of insider threats in your organization? (may select multiple)

- Current Employees Former Employees Contractors/Suppliers Competitors

4. What are the most common causes of security breaches in your industry / organization? (may select multiple)

- Weak physical security measures Ineffective cybersecurity policies Insider threats
 Lack of security awareness among employees Inadequate HR policies in recruitment and access control

5. How frequently does your organization conduct security audits or risk assessments? *

- Never Once a year Twice a year More than twice a year

Part 2: Zero Trust Security Model for IT & OT Protection

6. Whether your organization familiar with the 'Zero Trust Security Model' wherein no user device or application is considered trustworthy?

- Yes, it has been implemented Yes, but not implemented yet
 No, but we are considering adopting it No, not aware of it

7. What security controls does your organization implement for Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) network protection? (may select multiple)

- Network segmentation Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) End-to-end encryption
 Least Privilege Access Controls Security Information and Event Management (SIEM)
 None

8. How effective do you believe the Zero Trust model is in preventing cyber threats and data breaches?

- 1 2 3 4 5
Not Very Effective

Part 3: Layered Security Approach

9. What physical security measures does your organization use? (may select multiple) *

- CCTV Surveillance Perimeter Intrusion Detection Systems (PIDS)
- Gate Pass Management System (GPMS) streamlining visitor, material and vehicle entry
- Biometric Access Control Security Personnel / Guards Secure Facility Design
- None

10. What cybersecurity tools and protocols are employed in your organization? (may select multiple)

- Firewalls & Intrusion Detection Systems Secure Communication Channels (such as encrypted emails, VPNs) Identity & Access Management (IAM) Regular Cybersecurity Audits & Penetration Testing None

11. How effective is the layered security approach (integrating physical security, cybersecurity and HRM) in mitigating security threats?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely Effective				

12. Rate the effectiveness of your organization's current layered security approach in mitigating security threats.

	2	3	4	5	
Not	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely Effective

Part 4: Role of HR in Security Management

13. What HR policies are in practice in your organization to mitigate insider threats? (may select multiple)

- Background Verification for Employees Employee Access Control & Least Privilege Policy Security Awareness & Training Programs Whistleblower Protection Policy Exit Policies (ensuring ex-employees can't misuse sensitive info) None

14. Does your organization conduct Security Awareness Programs for employees? *

Yes, annually Yes, quarterly No, but planning to implement No

15. Which of the following topics are covered in HR led security training programs? (may select multiple)

- Cybersecurity best practices (e.g. password management, phishing awareness)
- Physical security protocols (e.g. access control, emergency evacuation)

Crisis communication and response Identifying, data collection, analysis and reporting threats Modus Operandi of Cybercriminals and case studies Cyber law None

16. How important is it for HR to collaborate with physical security and cybersecurity team to address workforce related risks during a crisis?

1 2 3 4 5
Not ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Extremely Important

17. How do you rate the effectiveness of HR policies in preventing security threats in your organization? *Mark only one oval.*

1 2 3 4 5
Not ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Very Effective

Part 5: Procurement and Supply Chain Security

18. Which of the following measures are currently in practice to secure your supply chain? (may select multiple)

Background verification of suppliers Monitoring of supply chain logistics
 Secure procurement contracts (e.g. clauses for security compliance) Cybersecurity compliance check such as ISO 27001 for IT assets Verification of hardware/software integrity (e.g. testing for malware) None

19. How vulnerable do you consider your organization's supply chain to threats like malicious software or faulty hardware from suppliers?

1 2 3 4 5
Not ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Highly Vulnerable

20. Rate the effectiveness of your organization's current procurement and supply chain security

1 2 3 4 5
Not ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ Highly Effective

Part 6: Security of Key Personnel / Person in high authority in Business and Critical Projects

21. Does your organization have specific security measures to identify and protect key personnel involved in critical projects or business operations?

Yes No May be

22. Rate the effectiveness of your organization's current measures in protecting key personnel from threats such as assault, kidnapping and exploitation etc. (Optional)

1 2 3 4 5
Not Highly Effective

Part 7: Developing an Integrated Security Plan

23. Which of the following components are included in your organization's existing security plan? (may select multiple)

Physical Security (e.g. Guards, PIDS, Access Controls) Cybersecurity (e.g. firewalls, IAM, penetration testing) HRM (e.g. employee training, background checks, crisis protocols)

24. How important is it to integrate physical security, cybersecurity and HRM into a single security plan to address industrial threats?

1 2 3 4 5
Not Extremely Important

25. Which of the following benefits do you expect from an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

Improved safety of personnel and assets Faster response time to incidents
 Greater operational efficiency Reduced risk of technology leakage or Intellectual Property theft Better preparedness for insider threats and cyber-attacks None

26. Which physical security measures should be prioritized in an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

Perimeter Intrusion Detection Systems (PIDS) Access Control Systems (e.g., biometric, keycards, entry pass) CCTV Surveillance Secure Facility Design Security Personnel / Guards

27. Which cybersecurity measures should be prioritized in an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

Zero Trust Model / Architecture Firewalls & Intrusion Detection Systems Identity & Access Management (IAM) Secure Communication Channels Regular Cybersecurity Audit / Penetration Testing

28. Which HRM practices should be prioritized in an integrated security plan? (may select multiple)

Security Awareness & Training Programs Background Checks for Employees

Crisis Response Protocols for Workforce Insider Threat Monitoring

Whistleblower Protection Policy

Exit Policies (ensuring ex-employees can't misuse sensitive information)

29. What do you consider the most critical emerging threat to industrial security in the next five years? (Optional)

30. Do you have any suggestions for integrating physical security, cybersecurity and HRM address technology leakage, insider threats and cyber-attacks? (Optional)

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